

Competency Behaviour and Innovative Teaching in State Religious Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract:

The study analysed the level of competency behaviour and the level of innovative teaching among state religious high school teachers. It is to overcome the problem of less successful teachers making students interested in subjects and teachers who are less successful at harnessing the potential of students' creativity and problem-solving activities. It uses the study design of the Quantitative Method, in which researchers collect and analysed data, integrate results, and draw conclusions using quantitative approaches. A total of 300 participants from the study responded to questionnaires on teacher competency behaviour and innovative teaching for quantitative studies. Researchers conducted a 16-week study. Researchers analysed quantitative data using SPSS Version 26 software. The study found that teachers have high-level competency behaviours in terms of professional knowledge-specific actions, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning. The study found that teachers have high-level competency behaviours in terms of professional knowledge-specific action, professional skills, lifelong learning, ethical standards and values, professional development, and personal characteristics. They have high-level innovative teaching skills with life and career skills, information skills, media, and technology, as well as teaching skills. It also has implications for the practice of lecturers, specialist teachers, experienced teachers, trainee teachers, and novice teachers.

Keywords: *Teacher Competency, Innovative Teaching, Competency Behaviour, Practice*

Introduction:

This innovative teaching and guidance on the use of innovation in teaching to teachers is important in the context of 21st century learning skills. It has various implications, especially for teachers and students. For teachers, innovatively improves the quality of teaching. While the implications for students are that innovative has an impact on learning effectiveness and learning satisfaction. What is most significant is that this field of study of creativity and innovation. It meets the requirements of the body of educational knowledge or the body of knowledge, that is, on the component of the specialization of education for secondary education.

According to Lund and Grams (2017), education is the process of influencing students' understanding, actions, belief systems, and attitudes. This is so that students dare to do different things. It is also so that students can think and act outside the box to express original thoughts and ideas. In this case, there is some rationale. Competence affects the goals, communication, values, behaviour, and practice of the teacher in school. It supports professional development and curriculum studies. In addition, teaching innovation encourages teachers and students to explore, research, and use all tools to reveal something new. It involves different ways of looking at the problem and solving it. It also helps students develop creativity and problem-solving skills.

This section deals with the statement of the issue of the study. Researchers analysed several past studies of this issue. It has benefits and importance to teachers and students. The literature review explores most of that research. This coincides with the sentiment that teachers can teach innovation to students. It is to develop the ability of students to analyse and make independent assessments. In addition, the teacher can stimulate the interest of students and motivate to learn. One thing is that this study examines an important issue, which is that teachers are less successful in drawing students' attention to learning in the classroom. One aspect of the

issue is that teachers are less successful in making students attracted to subjects. Moreover, less successful teachers make students want to learn more about the lesson (Karen, 2016).

According to Kathryn (2016), the specific issue of teachers is that the teacher does not master the core competencies of a professional teacher. Therefore, the teacher should identify the issue and overcome the specific problems of the teacher. In this regard, Guerriero and Révai (2017) state that the competence of a professional teacher consists of the competence of the content and pedagogical knowledge, the competence of affective motivation and beliefs, and the competence of the teaching approach. In addition, according to Guerriero and Révai, teachers are also less successful in harnessing the potential in terms of creativity and problem-solving. In addition, teachers are also less successful in improving the learning ability of students. Based on the findings of research by Karen (2016), Kathryn (2016), and Guerriero & Révai (2017), it is clear that there is indeed an issue in terms of the level of teacher competency behaviour and the level of innovative teaching among teachers, which the researchers investigated in this study.

The purpose of this section is to highlight the objectives of this research. We conducted the study based on the following research objectives:

1. To identify the level of competency behaviour of state religious high school teachers.
2. To analyse the level of innovative teaching among state religious high school teachers.

The meaning of this section is to ask this research question. We conduct research to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of competency behaviour of teachers in state religious high schools?
2. What is the level of innovative teaching among state religious high school teachers?

This section aims to elaborate on the limitations of this study. Researchers identified the limitations of the studies as follows, that is, in terms of the longitude effects for which the researchers selected research problems that did not require excessive time to complete the study of the literature, use the methodology, collect data, and interpret the results. Moreover, in terms of bias or bias which researchers are careful in selecting samples and respondents.

This section deals with the importance of the study. Researchers hope that this study will contribute to the body of educational knowledge in the component of the specialization of education for secondary education, that is, in the field of creativity and innovation studies. Innovative use guides in teaching are important in the context of 21st century learning skills. It has various implications such as innovation, improving the quality of teaching and the effectiveness of teachers. In addition, it also enhances creative thinking among students. Researchers expect that the results of this research contribute to the knowledge base in terms of innovative approaches, methods, and techniques in teaching. Innovative in teaching is significant for the teacher's understanding of teaching and learning, as it reflects the core competencies. Researchers may share the results of this research with students, teachers, lecturers, and educational experts.

The purpose of this section is to elaborate the definition for each variable of this study. Researchers identified two variables, namely competency behaviour and innovative teaching.

Competency Behaviour. In this study, competency behaviour refers to the specific actions of professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning among teachers. Researchers measured it using the 5-Point Likert Scale. Researchers used an instrument in the form of a Questionnaire by asking the teacher to respond to either 1 = Strongly Disagree, or 2 = Disagree, or 3 = Neutral, or 4 = Agree, or 5 = Very Agree.

Innovative Teaching. In this research, innovative teaching refers to teachers who teach with life and career skills, teaching and innovation skills, as well as information, media, and technology skills. In this regard, the researchers measured it using the 5-Point Likert Scale. Researchers use instruments in the form of Questionnaires by asking teachers to respond to either 5 = always practice innovation teaching skills, or 4 = Often practice innovation teaching skills all the time, or 3 = Sometimes practice skills teaching innovation when necessary, or 2 = Rarely practice innovation teaching skills, or 1 = Never practice innovation teaching skills.

Teacher at the State Religious High School. In this study, State Religious High School teachers referred to male teachers and female teachers who were teaching Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4 in all state religious

secondary schools.

Literature Review:

This section focuses on the theories underlying the research and the theoretical framework of this research. In this regard, the researcher selects a theory related to the field of research. Since researchers conducted studies on the quality of teacher competency and the use of innovating teaching, the two appropriate theories were the Teacher Competency Theory by Medley (1977) and the Concerns-Based Adoption Model by Hall & Hord (1987).

Teacher Competency Theory by Medley (1977). According to Medley (1977), the competence of the teacher refers to 5 types of components of the teacher's competence. It includes (1) Pre-direction: Teacher expectations and instruction planning are important directions for teaching and achieving desired results; (2) Presentation: Effective implementation of the teaching learning plan makes the most effective use of opportunities for all students; (3) Learning Environment: Supportive, safe and stimulating learning plans make the most effective use of opportunities for the development of student learning; (4) Student Learning: Assessment and adjustment of teaching improves student success and desired learning outcomes from teachers and student interaction; and (5) Professionalism: Professional behaviour and engagement, which extends beyond the classroom, which is better to enable teachers to assist students in learning.

The Concerns-Based Adoption Model by Hall & Hord (1987). The Concerns-Based Adoption Model (Hall & Hord, 1987) addresses each assumption about individual concerns about innovation. Furthermore, about the specific way innovations are delivered or implemented, and the adaptation of innovations to individuals. The principles and concepts of the model explain that change is a process, not an event. It takes time to apply the changes. Individuals must be in the spotlight if change is facilitated, and the institution will not change until its members change. The process of change is a very personal experience. Moreover, how it is perceived by the individual will greatly affect the result. Besides, individuals progress through various stages regarding their emotions and capabilities related to innovation. Availability of client-centered diagnostic or prescriptive models. It can improve individual facilities during staff development. The party responsible for the change process must work adaptively and systematically, where progress needs to be monitored continuously.

Study Theoretical Framework. In this study, the behaviour of the teacher's competence impacts the use of innovative teaching among teachers. Researchers describe these relationships and relevance in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Study Theoretical Framework

The purpose of this section is to elaborate related past studies and research conceptual framework. **Teacher's Competency Behaviour.** Every teacher constantly strives to be an effective educator. It wants to apply a lasting positive influence on student life. However, the question arises about what makes the teacher effective. In this regard, Stronge (2018) states that the teacher's framework for effective teaching is

professional knowledge, teacher professionalism, teaching planning, teaching delivery, assessment, and learning environment. Therefore, the teacher should strive to comply with quality standards.

In this regard, Alberta Education (2020) outlines as many as six standard characteristics of teacher quality as follows, namely: (1) teachers build positive and productive relationships with students, parents, guardians, peers, and others in schools and local communities to support student learning, (2) teachers develop and apply basic knowledge for of all students, (3) teachers create, promote, and maintaining an inclusive learning environment where the diversity of each student is maintained, respected, and safe, (4) teachers use up-to-date repertoire and comprehensive planning, instruction, and effective assessment practices to meet each student's learning needs, (5) teachers engage in professional learning careers and ongoing critical reflections to improve teaching and learning, and (6) teachers demonstrate understanding and compliance with the framework and legal basis that provides the basis for the national education system.

Innovative Teaching Among Teachers. In this regard, Stéphan, Joaquin, Soumyajit & Gwénaél (2019) identifies and describes four types of innovation as follows, namely: (1) product innovation is a good introduction or a new or significantly improved service in relation to the intended characteristics or uses. This includes significant improvements in technical specifications, components, and materials, incorporated software, user-friendliness, or other functional features; (2) organizational innovation is the implementation of new organizational methods in the business practices of firms, workplace organizations or external relations; (3) process innovation is the implementation of a new or significant production or delivery method. This includes significant changes in techniques, equipment, and software; (4) marketing innovation is the implementation of new marketing methods that involve significant changes in product design or packaging, product placement, product promotion, or price. The type of innovation related to teaching is process innovation. It's the implementation of a new or significant method. This includes significant changes in techniques and equipment.

According to Lee (2018), innovation in teaching is a design thought that helps students become more innovative. It involves process, practice, and design thinking teaching 21st-century skills. It involves conformity, collaboration, and critical thinking. Furthermore, it allows students to use creativity to address real-world issues. The goal is to achieve better results through the use of five phases of learning, namely empathy, determination, ideas, prototypes, and tests. Innovation in learning takes place in the context of teaching and learning, specifically to improve the implementation of standard practices or introduce new practices.

Murphy, Redding and Twyman (2019) noted that innovative practices can be a culture of innovation in educational organizations or throughout the organizational system. It systematically institutionalizes the innovation of the following five phases of the process, namely: (1) stimulates innovation to improve learning outcomes; (2) enable potential wearers to choose innovations according to their context and needs; (3) ensure that innovation is implemented with loyalty to its needs of elements and adaptations to enhance its effectiveness in a given context; (4) facilitate innovation through implementation in multiple classrooms, schools, and districts; and (5) provide a system to monitor the impact of innovation and scale, as well as implement the necessary changes.

Study Conceptual Framework. In this regard, the researcher builds a diagram to clearly illustrate the constructs or variables of this research. Its relevance and relationship are shown using the arrow, as in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Study Conceptual Framework

Methodology:

Research Design

The purpose of this section is to elaborate the design of this research. Researchers used the design of the Quantitative Method. In this regard, according to Creswell & Creswell (2018), the Quantitative Method is a research method by which researchers collect data, analyse data, integrate findings, and draw conclusions using quantitative approaches. In this research, the researcher uses the Quantitative Method Design approach, that is, the researcher conducts quantitative research independently, and then the researcher brings the interpretation. This approach is the choice of researchers because it benefits in terms of suitability, speed in data collection, and constraints that prevent researchers from pursuing other designs such as experimental designs that are not suitable for variable effects. The form of data collection is to use survey techniques through Questionnaire Forms. Researchers administer face-to-face in the field for data security.

Study Variables

In this research, the independent is the level of teacher competency behaviour among teachers. While the dependent variable is an innovative lesson.

Research Instruments

The meaning of this section is to elaborate on this research instrument. Researchers used four types of instruments to obtain data. These instruments are the Teacher's Demographic Information Questionnaire Form, a Questionnaire on Teacher's Competency Behaviour and a Questionnaire About Innovative Teaching,

Teacher's Demographic Information Questionnaire Form. This instrument aims to gather information on respondents who participate in this research. There are three items, namely gender, academic qualifications, and teaching experience.

Questionnaire on Teacher Competency Behaviour. This instrument aims to obtain respondents' feedback in terms of competency behaviour based on five constructs, namely professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, as well as professional development and lifelong learning. Researchers used the Five-Point Likert Scale to measure the very agree = 5, agree = 4,

neutral = 3, disagree = 2, and very disagree = 1.

Questionnaire About Innovative Teaching. This instrument aims to obtain respondents' feedback in terms of innovative teaching based on three constructs, namely life and career skills, information skills, media, and technology, as well as teaching and innovation skills. Researchers used the Five-Point Likert Scale to measure the level of Always Practice Skills Teaching Innovation All the Time (5), Often Practising Skills Teaching Innovation All the Time (4), Sometimes Practice Skills Teaching Innovation, When Necessary (3), Rarely Practice Skills Teaching Innovation (2), and Never Practice Innovation Teaching Skills (1).

Research Validity

The purpose of this section is to describe the validity of this research in terms of external validity and internal validity.

External Validity. This section refers to external validity. It has several assumptions. As follows, namely: (i) that the findings can be applied to the study population, study location, and different study periods, despite having low ecological validity. This is because the location of the study was only concentrated in the state religious secondary school only for a period of 16 weeks; (ii) that inferences can be made to the population based on the findings of this study despite having low population validity because the study participants were not randomly selected independent of the target population, but the study participants were drawn from among the teachers who taught Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4 only.

Internal Validity. This section refers to the internal validity. It has the assumption of the study as follows: (i) that the effect on the dependent variable, that is, innovative teaching is solely due to non-dependent variables, that is, the behaviour of the teacher's competence and the constraints of innovative teaching among teachers; (ii) that the historical variable is not interfering with the internal validity of this study due to the short study duration, which is only 16 weeks.

Reliability of Research Instruments

The meaning of this section is to determine the reliability of this research instrument. Researchers conducted a pilot study to determine the reliability of the Questionnaire question item. This study has high reliability for the following reason, which is that this study has used a panel of Questionnaire item assessors consisting of qualified experts who have been working in the field for a long time. The scores obtained by the study participants in the Five-Point Likert Scalable Questionnaire Question during the pilot study were determined alpha values by using the Cronbach alpha coefficient formula.

According to Taber (2018), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.94), strong (0.91–0.93), reliable (0.84–0.90), strong (0.81), relatively high (0.76–0.95), high (0.73–0.95), good (0.71–0.91), relatively high (0.70–0.77), slightly low (0.68), reasonable (0.67–0.87), adequate (0.64–0.85), medium (0.61–0.65), satisfactory (0.58–0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.98), insufficient (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.93– 0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), inadequate (0.45–0.96), alpha values are described as outstanding (0.97), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0.45–0.96), satisfactory (0.96), acceptable (0.45–0.98), inadequate (0), unsatisfactory (0.4–0.55), and low (0.11).

Based on the results of this pilot study, the value of Cronbach's alpha coefficient after analysis using SPSS software Version 26 is as follows, that is, for the Questionnaire Question on Teacher Competency Behaviour, Cronbach's alpha value is $\alpha = 0.85$, that is, reliable. Whereas for Questionnaire Questions About Innovative Teaching, Cronbach's alpha value is $\alpha = 0.81$, that is, strong.

Study Population

In this study, the researchers had a study population of 1129 teachers from 23 State Religious Secondary Schools (Department of Islamic Religion, Selangor, Malaysia, 2019).

Study Sampling

In this study, researchers used layered random sampling to select samples among the population. The characteristics of the sample or respondent are as follows, namely gender, male teacher and female teacher who is teaching Form 1, Form 2, and Form 4. The number of teachers, namely male teachers and female teachers is 15 – 20 for a school. In this research, researchers used the Sample Size Determination Table by Krejcie & Morgan (1970) to determine the sample size based on the study population. Based on table determine the sample size with N, which is the study population of 1129 people, then S, that is, the study sample is 300 people. The summary of the sample profile of this study is as per Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of Study Sample Profile

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Men	47	17%
Female	253	83%
Total	300	100%

Academic Qualifications	Frequency	Percentage
Graduate	195	65%
Non-Graduate	105	35%
Total	300	100%

Experience	Frequency	Percentage
Ten Years and Down	84	28%
Eleven Years and Above	216	72%
Total	300	100%

Study Ethics

Researchers adhere to research ethics by following recommendations by Cresswell & Cresswell (2018). In this study, the researchers ensured an adequate sample size to ensure sufficient strength power. In addition, the researchers did not repair or top up the data collected. Researchers did not replicate studies made by other researchers. Further, we also reported conflicting studies. Furthermore, the researchers included findings despite the negative findings and reported alternative explanations. Next, the researchers shared the findings and data with other researchers by publishing the results of the study. Then, the researchers measured control units such as age, gender, and race. Finally, researchers use conceptual or theoretical models as a guide in choosing variables so that all expectations are considered.

Results and Discussion:

Level of Competency Behaviour of State Religious High School Teachers. The purpose of this section is to identify the level of competency behaviour of teachers at state religious high schools. Researchers use survey techniques to collect quantitative data. Researchers analysed quantitative data to find mean or average Central Tendency by using SPSS Version 26 software. The results of the analysis as in Table 2.

Table 2. Levels of Teacher Competency Behaviour

Teacher Competency	Score	Min	Frequency	Percentage
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Behaviour Level		Score		
High Level	66 – 90	66	153	51%
Low Level	48 – 65		147	49%
Total			300	100%

Based on Table 2, the mean or average score is 66 and the top score of the mean indicates the high level, while the lower score of the mean indicates the low level. The study found that high-level competency behaviour among teachers was 51% compared to low-level competency behaviour of 49%. This suggests that teachers with high-level competency behaviours are more numerous than teachers with low-level competency behaviours. The study found that state religious high school teachers have high-level competency behaviour in terms of specific actions of professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning.

Levels of Innovative Teaching Among State Religious Secondary School Teachers. This section aims to analyse the level of innovative teaching among teachers at state religious secondary schools. Researchers use survey techniques to collect quantitative data. Researchers analysed quantitative data to find mean or average Central Tendency by using SPSS Version 26 software. The results of the analysis as in Table 3.

Table 3. Teaching Innovative Levels

Teaching Innovative Levels	Score	Min Score	Frequency	Percentage
High Level	85 – 100	85	174	61%
Low Level	53–84		126	39%
Total			300	100%

Based on Table 3, the mean or average score is 85 and the top score of the mean indicates a high level, while the lower score of the mean indicates a low level. The study found that the highest level of innovative teaching among teachers was 61% compared to the low level of innovative teaching at 39%. This shows that teachers with high-level innovative teaching skills are more numerous than teachers with low-level innovative teaching skills. The study found that state religious high school teachers have high-level innovative teaching skills by having teaching and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, as well as life and career skills.

Conclusion:

Study Findings Summary

The meaning of this section is to summarize the findings of this study. The study found that state religious high school teachers have high-level competency behaviour in terms of specific actions of professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning. In addition, they also have high-level innovative teaching skills with teaching and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, as well as life and career skills.

Study Findings Discussion

The main findings of this study show that teachers with high-level competency behaviours are teachers who have specific actions of professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning. It is in line with the findings of the Stronge study (2018) which found that a teacher's framework for effective teaching is professional knowledge, teaching planning, teaching delivery, assessment, learning environment, and teacher professionalism. This finding is also supported by Alberta Education (2020) which states that every teacher

must strive to comply with teacher quality standards, that is, teachers engage in professional learning careers and ongoing critical reflections to improve teaching and learning.

In addition, the study also found that teachers with high-level innovative teaching skills are teachers with teaching and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, as well as life and career skills. This finding is also supported by Lee (2018) who states that innovation in teaching is a design mindset that helps students become more innovative by engaging processes, practices, and design thinking teaching 21st-century skills such as suitability, collaboration, and critical thinking. It is in line with the findings of the Murphy, Redding and Twyman (2019) study which found that innovative practices can be a culture of innovation, in educational organizations or across organizational systems, systematically.

Study Implications

This section deals with the implications of this study. The main findings show that teachers with high-level competency behaviours are teachers who have specific actions of professional knowledge, professional skills, personal characteristics, ethical standards and values, professional development, and lifelong learning. It has implications for the practice of teachers, trainee teachers, novice teachers, experienced teachers, expert teachers, and lecturers.

The findings of this study show that teachers with high-level innovative teaching skills are teachers with teaching and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, as well as life and career skills. It also has implications for the practice of teachers, trainee teachers, novice teachers, experienced teachers, expert teachers, and lecturers.

It has implications for the practice of teachers, lecturers, school nazirs, curriculum officers, exam officers, administrators, policymakers, parents, and community members. In addition, the findings of this study in terms of theory and policy contribute to the body of educational knowledge in the component of the specialization of education for secondary education, namely in the field of creativity and innovation studies.

Suggestions

The purpose of this section is to submit proposals. In this regard, researchers suggest that school nazirs, curriculum officers, examination officers, administrators, policymakers, parents, and community members solve the issue of teachers who lack or lack knowledge and skills in the use of innovative teaching. In addition, the researchers also proposed further research on this topic at the primary school level.

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